

Groundwater Contamination by Fluoride and Nitrate in the Pullamapatti Watershed, Tamil Nadu: A Health Risk Assessment

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Key Points:

- The Pullamapatti watershed faces significant groundwater quality issues, including high fluoride and nitrate levels, posing health risks like fluorosis and methemoglobinemia, particularly for children.
- Groundwater occurrence is controlled by weathered and fractured crystallines, with rainfall variability and anthropogenic activities contributing to contamination trends.
- Effective groundwater monitoring, optimized agricultural practices, and pollution control measures are essential for mitigating health risks and ensuring long-term water resource sustainability.

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Abstract

Drinking water that has elevated levels of fluoride (F^-) and nitrate (NO_3^-) can be extremely harmful to our health. The present study investigates the hydrogeological and geochemical characteristics of the Pullamapatti watershed, underlain by Archean crystallines with alluvial deposits in limited areas. Groundwater occurs primarily in weathered and fractured crystalline rocks under phreatic and semi-confined conditions, with transmissivity values ranging from 12 to 300 m^2/day and a specific yield of less than 4%. Long-term water-level data (1998–2023) indicate a mixed trend of rise and fall, reflecting localized recharge and extraction patterns. Hydrochemical analysis reveals elevated concentrations of fluoride (0.19–3.60 mg/L) and (NO_3^-) (up to 229 mg/L), surpassing permissible limits in several locations, driven by geological, agricultural, and anthropogenic influences. Spatio-temporal variations in water quality underscore the role of aquifer mineralogy, fertilizer use, and wastewater discharge in contaminant loading. Health risk assessments show significant non-carcinogenic risks, especially for children, through intake and dermal exposure to fluoride and nitrate. Health risk assessments identify children as more vulnerable to fluoride and nitrate exposure, with higher hazard indices compared to adults. In 2023, 30% of the watershed area posed no significant non-carcinogenic risk ($THI < 1$), while 70% showed significant risks ($THI > 1$). In contrast, over 90% of the area in 2015 and 2019 faced significant health risks, highlighting a reduction in affected areas over time but emphasizing the need for continued mitigation in high-risk zones and community awareness to safeguard water quality in the region.

Keywords: Health Risk Assessment, Hazard Index, Non-Carcinogenic Risk, Hydrogeological, Aquifer

1. Introduction

Safe drinking water supply remains a critical issue worldwide, posing public health threats nowadays due to natural causes, unscientific urbanization, climatic changes, and anthropogenic interventions (Dilpazeer et al., 2023; Kamruzzaman et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2018). Around 2.5

billion people around the world depend on groundwater sources for potable purposes and their daily needs (Ghani et al., 2022; McDonald et al., 2011). Long-term consumption of contaminated groundwater results in serious health issues for human populations and other organisms (Majolagbe et al., 2016; Su et al., 2021). It is estimated that around 80% of health-related problems in the world are

linked to the consumption of inferior quality potable water, while 65% of endemic diseases in arid and semi-arid regions are due to the ingestion of water with high fluoride content (Narsimha and Sudarshan, 2017).

Groundwater contamination by fluoride (F^-) and nitrate (NO_3^-) has been a leading public health concern over the last twenty years, and they were included under international regulations due to their adverse impacts on human health (Qasemi et al., 2023). India is one of the nations in the world experiencing significant health issues due to groundwater contamination, particularly with respect to F^- and nitrate. Elevated fluoride levels, specifically those exceeding 1.5 mg/L (WHO, 2011), can cause dental and skeletal fluorosis. These conditions are associated with symptoms such as ventricular abnormalities, muscle weakness, excessive sweating, and tachycardia (Adimalla et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020). While there are anthropogenic sources like fertilizers and the aluminum industry, continuous population growth and unregulated groundwater extraction, especially in developing nations, are likely to increase contamination from geological fluoride sources (Ayoob and Gupta, 2006; Kundu and Mandal, 2009). Elevated nitrate concentrations exceeding 45 mg/L are closely linked to severe health risks, including methemoglobinemia (blue baby syndrome) in infants, birth defects, and the potential formation of carcinogens through reactions with other compounds (Chen et al., 2017; Ransom et al., 2022). The contamination of groundwater with nitrates has been ongoing for many years, largely caused by the use of agricultural chemicals, fertilizers, runoff from municipal landfills, sewage, and various industrial discharges (Liu et al., 2021). The daily amount of F^- and NO_3^- that enters the digestive system has a direct correlation with its health effects. However, the volume of water consumed and the magnitude of F^- and NO_3^- intake vary significantly depending on the climate. As a result, the precise conditions are not always highlighted by the suggested guideline values. The Bureau of Indian Standards was taken into consideration for analysis in this study. In India and around the world, groundwater F^- and NO_3^- enrichment is a hot topic (Saxena and Ahmed, 2001). The USEPA has set a maximum permissible limit of 10 mg/L for nitrate (NO_3^-) in water (Beaver et al., 2014).

Health risk assessment methods systematically provide quantitative or semi-quantitative evaluations of potential

human or environmental health impacts from contaminant exposure. Human health risks connected with inhalation, ingestion, and dermal exposure to contaminated water need important attention (USEPA, 2014). In the present study, F^- and NO_3^- contamination and associated health risk assessments over the Pullamapatti watershed of Northern Tamil Nadu have been conducted. The objectives of this study include: (1) determining the F^- and NO_3^- contamination in the Pullamapatti watershed; (2) investigating the processes responsible for the enrichment of fluoride (F^-) and nitrate (NO_3^-) in groundwater; and (3) evaluating the potential health risks associated with human exposure to these contaminants through groundwater consumption and dermal exposure.

2. Study Area

The Pullamapatti watershed extends 1701.69 km² in the Indian state of Tamil Nadu, encompassing the districts of Dharmapuri and Krishnagiri. It is situated between the longitude between 78°00' and 78°35'E and the latitude between 12°00' and 12°31'N. The main drainage in the area is the Ponnaiyar River, which splits into the Pullamapatti and Semmandakuppam rivers near Kambainellur. The location map of the study area is depicted in Figure 1.

Undulating plains, upland plateaus, and Archaean crystallines such as gneissic and charnockite rocks are the region's defining features. In the north and northeast of the district, gneissic crystalline formations can be found. Whereas Peninsular Gneiss is found in Krishnagiri and portions of Kaveripaattinam, Granitic Gneiss is more common in the Shoolagiri and Kelamangalam regions. Parts of Harur, Uthangarai, and Morappur have foliated gneiss, whereas parts of Kariamangalam, Palacode, and Uthangarai have biotite gneiss. The southern region, which includes parts of Dharmapuri, Pennagaram, Nallampalli, Palacode, Morappur, and Pappireddipatti, is dominated by Charnockite. Quartzites occur sporadically, particularly in the Denganikottai block. Additionally, dolerite dykes of varying lengths intersect the district's country rock. On either side of the river courses, alluvial deposits are reported, which transport sediments by the rivers Ponnaiyar and Chinnar. The regional geological setting of the area is compiled (Table 1). The climate is arid to semi-arid with an average precipitation of 858.56 mm for 2015–2023 and an annual average maximum daily temperature of 29.5°C.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area.

Table 1: : Regional geological setting of the Pullamapatti watershed (Modified after Department of Mining & Geology and GSI, 2016).

Age	Group	Lithology
U. Proterozoic	Alkali/Ultramafic Complex	Aplite: Quartz-barites veins: Pegmatite
		Felsites Porphyry biotite dyke
		Carbonatite
		Syenite
		Anorthosites
		Pyroxenites, Gabbro, Dunite
		Epidote-hornblende gneiss
		Dolerite
Archean to L. Proterozoic	Kolar	Granite
		Metabasalt, Metagabbro
Archean	Peninsular Gneissic Complex	Pink migmatite
		Granitoid gneiss
	Sargur/Satgyamangalam	Amphibolite
		Cordierite-sillimanite-mica schist
		Fuchsite Quartzite
	Migmatite Complex	Hornblende-biotite gneiss
		Garnetiferous quartzo-feldspathic gneiss
	Ultrabasic Complex	Gabbro/pyroxenite
	Charnockite Group	Magnetite quartzite
		Pyroxene granulite
Charnockite		
Khondalite Group	Quartzite	
	Garnet-sillimanite gneiss	

3. Methodology

Figure 2: Methodology used in the study.

Detailed hydrogeological studies were conducted in the Pullamapatti watershed. Key wells were established for water level monitoring and sampling. Groundwater samples were collected from dug and bore wells, covering the entire study area. *In situ* parameters (pH, EC, TDS, and temperature) were measured in the field itself, and samples were collected and properly labeled. These samples were analyzed in the laboratory for physicochemical parameters such as total hardness (TH) and major ions. The analysis techniques were standardized in accordance with APHA guidelines (APHA, 2022). *In situ* parameters were measured using a pH/EC/TDS meter (Hanna HI 9811-5). The titrimetric method involving standard EDTA was employed for the determination of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . Chloride levels were estimated through $AgNO_3$ titration. The titration technique, following the standard procedure (APHA, 2022), was used for estimating carbonate and bicarbonate. Sodium (Na^+) and potassium (K^+) concentrations were measured using a flame photometer (Model 130 Systronics Flame Photometer). SO_4^{2-} was quantified via colorimetry

using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Furthermore, fluoride and nitrate concentrations in the water were assessed electrochemically using a fluoride Continuous Flow Analyzer. Along with field data collected during the year 2022, secondary data were obtained from the Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), SECR, Chennai for the present study. Variations in fluoride and nitrate were plotted using MATLAB, and the land use and land cover map was prepared using ArcGIS software. The overall methodology of the study is presented in the flowchart (Figure 2).

3.1. Health Risk Assessment

Adverse health impacts may occur due to continuous inhalation, drinking, and dermal exposure to certain chemical constituents over a period of time. The Nitrate and Fluoride form such contaminants in groundwater, which are chosen for the human health risk assessment in the present study. First, estimating the Average Daily Dosage (ADD) using the oral ingestion procedure, and then the hazard quotient (HQ), the total hazard index (THI) was calculated using the equations (Equation 1 – Equation 5) as shown in Table 2.

In this equation, ADD_{IN} and ADD_{DE} represent the average daily dosage of ingestion (mg/kg/day) and dermal exposure, respectively. Key parameters for assessing groundwater contaminant exposure include contaminant concentration (CPW) in mg/L, ingestion rates of 2.5 L/day for adults and 0.78 L/day for children, and exposed skin area (16,600 cm^2 for adults, 12,000 cm^2 for children). Annual exposure durations are 64 years for men, 67 years for women, and 12 years for children, with daily water exposure times of 0.4 hours for all groups. Dermal permeability (KP) and conversion factors (CF) are set at 0.001. Average body weights are 65 kg for men, 55 kg for women, and 15 kg for children. Average exposure durations (AET) are 23,360 days for adults, 4,380 days for children, and 365 days for infants. These metrics are essential for evaluating ingestion and dermal absorption risks from groundwater.

HQ_{IN} is the ingestion-based Hazard Quotient; HQ_{DE} is the dermal-based Hazard Quotient. RfD is the reference dosage, 0.04 mg/kg/day and 1.6 mg/kg/day for fluoride and NO_3^- , respectively. The total hazard index (THI) represents the total risk of exposure through digestion and dermal pathways (Equation 6). The THI and its remarks are compiled in Table 3.

Table 2: Equations of health risk assessment

Health Risk Assessments	Equation	References
Average Daily Dosage, ADD	$ADD_{IN} = \frac{CPW \times ED \times EF \times IR}{ABW \times AET}$	(1) Li and Wu, 2019 Selvam et al., 2020 Iqbal et al., 2023 USEPA, 2014
	$ADD_{DE} = \frac{CPW \times ED \times EF \times ET \times SA \times KP \times CF}{ABW \times AET}$	(2)
Hazard Quotient, HQ	$HQ_{IN} = \frac{ADD_{IN}}{RfD}$	(3) USEPA, 2005 USEPA, 2014
	$HQ_{DE} = \frac{ADD_{DE}}{RfD}$	(4)
Total Hazard Index, THI	$THI = \sum HI_f + \sum HI_{NO_3}$	(5) USEPA, 2005 USEPA, 2014

$$HI = \sum HQ_{IN} + \sum HQ_{DE} \tag{6}$$

Table 3: Total Hazard Index

Total Hazard Index	Remarks
$THI > 1$	Significant non-carcinogenic health hazards
$THI < 1$	No significant non-carcinogenic risk

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Hydrogeology

The Pullamapatti watershed is underlain by Archean crystallines with alluvial formations covering a limited aerial extension along the major river. The major aquifer systems consist of (i) unconsolidated and semi-consolidated formations, and (ii) weathered and fractured crystallines. Groundwater occurs in the weathered and fractured crystallines under phreatic to semi-confined conditions. The thickness of the weathered material ranges widely, from less than one meter below ground level (bgl) to more than twenty meters bgl. West of Dharmapuri and in the Pappireddipatti regions, sections of alluvium are interlaced with crystalline outcrops (Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), 2007).

The water level in the area rose between 0.0225 and 0.5744 meters per year, according to long-term water level variations from 1998 to 2021, and fell between 0.0600 and 0.6789 meters per year. Figure 3 describes the water level fluctuations along the Pullamapatti watershed in 2022 and 2023.

In weathered, partially weathered, and jointed rocks, transmissivity values range from 12 to 300 m²/day, with a specific yield of less than 2%. In other formations, transmissivity values vary between 4 and 16 m²/day, and the specific yield is approximately 2% to 4%.

Figure 3: Water level variation in Pullamapatti watershed in 2022 & 2023.

Figure 4: Trend of precipitation changes in Pullamapatti watershed, Dharmapuri district (2023 to 2015) (bars represent rainfall and line represent temperature).

In the higher areas of Krishnagiri taluks, temperatures are 2°C to 3°C lower, offering pleasant weather year-round. The plains also enjoy generally pleasant weather, except for occasional oppressive and sultry days in May, June, and July when temperatures peak around 36°C. Overall, the district’s climate is slightly humid. The trend of precipitation and temperature changes (2015–2023) in the Pullamapatti watershed, Dharmapuri district, is shown in Figure 4, with average rainfall and temperature between 2015–2023 compiled in Table 4.

Table 4: Trend of precipitation changes in Pullamapatti watershed, Dharmapuri district (Data Source: IMD)

No.	Year	Temperature (°C)	Rainfall (mm)
1	2023	29	1176.2
2	2022	30	1086
3	2021	27	967.9
4	2020	29	839.3
5	2019	30	435.2
6	2018	30	820.8
7	2017	29	622.4
8	2016	29.5	895.7
9	2015	28	883.6

Table 5: Max. and Min. values of chemical parameters in the groundwater samples (2022). **HDL**-Highest Desirable Limit; **MPL**-Maximum Permissible Limit

Water Quality Parameter		BIS (2012) HDL - MPL	WHO (2022)	Concentration in the Pullamapatti Watershed (min-max)	Average
pH		6.5-8.5	6.5 - 8.5	6.66 - 8.97	7.4
EC	$\mu S/cm$	-	1000	718 - 6780	2268
TDS	mg/L	500-2000	1000	531 - 4746	1547
TH		200-600	300	65 - 1865	638
Ca ²⁺		75-200	200	10 - 236	116
Mg ²⁺		30-100	150	13 - 400	127
Na ⁺		50 - 200	200	33 - 990	214
K ⁺		-	12	1 - 43	5
HCO ₃ ⁻		-	250	175 - 585	348
Cl ⁻		250-1000	250	92 - 1370	445
SO ₄ ²⁻		200-600	250	74 - 267	122
F ⁻		0.5-1.5	1.5	0.19 - 3.60	1.60
NO ₃ ⁻		45	50	3.16 - 106.55	16.57

4.2. Groundwater geochemistry

The hydrochemical characteristics of groundwater in the phreatic zone of the Pullamapatti watershed have been analyzed using field study and data of groundwater samples collected from the CGWB. Variation in fluoride and nitrate concentration, and its potential health risk assessment over the watershed, is studied in the present work. A statistical summary of the measured physico-chemical parameters for the groundwater samples of 2022 is compiled (Table 5) and compared to the WHO (2022) and BIS (2012) guidelines for drinking water.

Physico-chemical analysis shows that groundwater in the study area is generally alkaline, with pH values ranging from 6.6 to 8.79 (avg. 7.4), mostly within the WHO (2006) acceptable range of 7–8.5. Electrical Conductivity (EC) varies widely from 781 to 6780 $\mu S/cm$, averaging 2268 $\mu S/cm$, with over 50% of samples showing moderate salt enrichment. TDS range from 531 to 4746 mg/L, with most samples exceeding the WHO’s limit of 500 mg/L, and only

20% below 1500 mg/L. Total Hardness (TH) ranges from 65 to 1865 mg/L (average 638 mg/L), with 40% of samples below the limit of 500 mg/L, classifying the majority as hard to very hard water. Sodium concentrations (33–990 mg/L) exceed the WHO limit of 200 mg/L, while magnesium levels (13–400 mg/L) surpass the permissible limit of 150 mg/L in most samples. Calcium concentrations range from 10 to 236 mg/L, and potassium from 1 to 43 mg/L, with only 5% exceeding the limit of 10 mg/L. Chloride levels (92–1370 mg/L) exceed 600 mg/L in 20% of samples, influenced by domestic effluents, fertilizers, and mineral weathering. Nitrate varies between 3.16 to 106.55, with an average value of 16.57. Sulfate concentrations range from 74 to 267 mg/L, primarily derived from mineral dissolution. Weathering of aquifer materials, human activities, and geogenic sources contribute to elevated salinity and ion concentrations. Key minerals influencing water quality include amphiboles, feldspars, fluorite, and apatite in the granitic terrain.

Table 6: Fluoride and nitrate concentration (mg/L) in Pullamapatti watershed 2015-2023.

Location	2023		2022		2021		2019	
	NO ₃ ⁻	F ⁻						
Bharathipuram	15	0.54	30.9	0.33	59	0.54	50	0.68
Dharmapuri2	1	1.62	80.2	0.31	59	0.54	28	0.61
Irumattur new	14	0.1	20.7	0.54	11	0.8	56	0.5
Karthankulam DW	27	1.14	40.2	1.04	20	0.14	56	0.9
Morappur dw	51	1.44	62	0.96	65	0.42	88	0.75
Odasalapatti	4	0.56	66.6	0.78	81	1.46	78	1.3
Odasalapatti x road	54	0.98	156.7	0.9	62	0.47	79	0.78
Karukkanchavadi	30	0.83	17.8	0.72	8.8	0.99	26	0.89
Kaveripattinam	20	0.59	8.3	0.64	24	0.6	32	0.28
Machinkanakottai	7	1.29	6.9	1.29	10	1.4	11	1.57
Papparapatti	36	1.52	47	1.56	36	1.41	39	1.8
Panneswara Madam	170	1.29	166	1.3	121	1.6	114	0.93
Tattarhalli	11	0.71	11.3	0.61	67	1.6	50	1.21
Maniyampadi	8	0.74	51.6	0.52			9.7	2.9
Location	2018		2017		2016		2015	
	NO ₃ ⁻	F ⁻						
Bharathipuram	67	0.74	40	0.9	29	0.78	74	0.85
Dharmapuri2	31	0.82	50	0.3	44	0.64	52	0.4
Irumattur new	81	0.42	7	0.24	46	2.2	40	0.11
Karthankulam DW	76.1	1.4	40	0.96	48	0.32	58	0.42
Morappur dw	153.1	1.5	60	1.78	58	0.78	118	1.22
Odasalapatti	120	0.56	160	0.64	78	0.65	37	1.02
Odasalapatti x road	95	1.1	160	0.64	86	0.54	42	0.53
Karukkanchavadi	229	0.57	20	0.52	20	0.52	21.2	0.65
Kaveripattinam	28	0.5	10	0.71	18	0.4	35	0.43
Machinkanakottai	19	1.68	210.8	0.72	18.6	0.99	27	1.6
Papparapatti	55.9	1.6	53.8	1.76	44	1.54	34	1.06
Panneswara Madam	154	1.4	280.4	1.65	75.78	1.2	87	0.8
Tattarhalli	49	1.53	98.2	2.6	43.4	1.8	50	1.7
Maniyampadi								

4.3. Groundwater Fluoride and Nitrate in Pullamapatti watershed (2015-2023)

Secondary data collected between 2015 and 2023 from the Central Ground Water Department for the present study. Fluoride and nitrate data were analyzed and used for the health risk assessment in the Pullamapatti watershed. The F^- and NO_3^- concentrations in the groundwater samples vary between 2015 and 2023 and are compiled (Table 6).

In the Pullamapatti watershed, fluoride concentrations ranged from 0.33 to 2.6 mg/L. The international limit for fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg/L (WHO, 2011), which is the maximum permissible limit according to the Indian standard (BIS 2012), followed in the study. According to BIS (2012) guidelines, the permissible fluoride concentration in groundwater for maintaining dental and skeletal health is between 0.6 and 1.2 mg/L. Levels below 0.6 mg/L may lead to dental caries, while concentrations exceeding 1.5 mg/L can cause dental fluorosis and, in some cases, skeletal fluorosis.

4.4. Fluoride

The Figure 5 presents fluoride concentration trends (in mg/L) from 2015 to 2023 across various locations in the Pullamapatti watershed. Several sites, including Irumattur New, Karukkanchavadi, and Machinkanakottai, show noticeable fluctuations in fluoride levels, with some years exceeding the permissible limit (> 1.5 mg/L), suggesting potential groundwater quality concerns. Other locations, such as Odasalapatti, also exhibit variability in fluoride concentrations, with occasional peaks approaching the limit. However, places like Bharathipuram, Panneswara Madam, and Tattarhalli display relatively stable fluoride levels, staying consistently within maximum permissible limits. Papparapatti also shows minor fluctuations but remains well below the threshold. These temporal variations in fluoride levels may result from changes in groundwater recharge, evaporation, or human activities.

Fluoride levels in groundwater increase along flow paths due to the dissolving of fluoride-rich minerals like amphibole, biotite, fluorite, and apatite, commonly found in gneisses and granites. The geology of the study area, dominated by pink granites, charnockite, and various gneisses, serves as a major source of these minerals. Factors such as

pH, temperature, aquifer properties, residence time, porosity, and carbonate concentrations facilitate fluoride release, leading to elevated levels in groundwater. In the study area, all groundwater samples were alkaline, a condition that promotes the desorption of fluoride ions from various minerals, thereby enhancing the leaching process (Saxena and Ahmed, 2001; Wodeyar and Sreenivasan, 1996).

4.5. Nitrate

The Figure 6 illustrates nitrate concentration trends (in mg/L) from 2015 to 2023 across various locations in Pullamapatti watershed. Most sites show fluctuating nitrate levels over the years, with some peaks exceeding the maximum permissible limits (>45 mg/L). Notably, Karukkanchavadi (17.8 - 229) and Machinkanakottai (10 - 210) exhibit significant concentrations of nitrate, suggesting localized contamination issues, while Irumattur New, Odasalapatti, and Kaveripattinam also experience occasional elevated nitrate levels. On the other hand, areas like Papparapatti, Panneswara Madam, and Tattarhalli maintain stable trends with low nitrate concentrations. Although some locations keep nitrate levels within the acceptable limit, the concerning high concentration in others emphasizes the need for targeted groundwater quality management. In 2017, almost all locations recorded increased concentrations of NO_3^- in the groundwater. In 2022 and 2023, the nitrate levels across the study area showed a slight decline, attributed to the increase in rainfall and the implementation of more focused groundwater management strategies. High NO_3^- levels in the groundwater were found in the south and northeast parts of the Pullamapatti watershed, which is due to household garbage and agronomic activities.

Nitrate in the majority of locations is above the maximum permissible limit by WHO (2022) and BIS (2012). The nitrate levels in water are influenced mainly by meteorology, hydrology, and human activities. Other factors include soil particle size, aquifer media, soil water holding capacity, rainfall intensity, and the depth of the water table (Buvaneshwari et al., 2017; Minet et al., 2017). Their relation to nitrate, temperature, and precipitation has been studied, showing that air temperature increases nitrate levels, while precipitation decreases them (Jacobs et al., 2017). Meteorological data show fluctuations in Pullamapatti Watershed's average air temperature and precipitation during the reporting period Table 4.

Figure 5: Fluoride concentration along Pullamapatti watershed between 2015 and 2023 (data source: CGWB).

Figure 6: Nitrate variation between 2015 and 2023 (data source: CGWB, Chennai).

4.6. Land use land cover (LULC)

The LULC map (Figure 7) of the Pullamapatti watershed illustrates a variety of land categories, such as vegetation, agricultural crops, rangelands, built-up areas, bare ground, and water bodies. Vegetation and agricultural areas are predominant, with rangelands and built-up zones dispersed across the region. Water bodies and flooded vegetation are localized, highlighting the watershed's hydrological importance. The map showcases the diverse LULC patterns and their potential impact on water resources in the area.

Agricultural activities dominate the watershed, with crops covering the largest area, amounting to 10,257.14 km², indicating the region's significant reliance on agriculture. About 70-80% of the Pullamapatti watershed is cropland, indicating the higher usage of fertilizers in the watershed area.

Recent studies indicate that nitrate (NO₃) demand in soils has increased over time (Fertilizer Association of India (FAI), 2010). Fertilizers are likely a significant source of groundwater nitrate in the region. The extensively black, loamy, and red soil along the Pullamapatti watershed may easily transmit surface contaminants to the water, resulting in the enrichment of contaminants (nitrate) in the groundwater.

4.7. Non-carcinogenic Health Risks Assessment

Contaminated ground water ingestion may cause many serious health impacts to human and other living beings. Fluoride and nitrate are two of the major contaminants in ground water. Continuous consumption and exposure to fluoride and nitrate enriched groundwater for a longer period of time may leads to serious health hazards. Various studies were conducted on health risk associated with F-contamination in ground water (Adimalla and Qian, 2020; Mukherjee and Singh, 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

Infants and children are highly susceptible to the nitrate toxicity (Blue baby syndrome) through the consumption of drinking ground water. Direct consumption of NO₃ through food and drinking water may leads to higher risk than other ways. The 3 to 21% of the NO₃ in to the human body is mainly through drinking water when compare with other sources like leafy vegetables, meat etc. (Wogan et al., 1995).

In present study health risk related with ingestion and dermal exposure to contaminated ground water has been examined. Total hazard index during 2015, 2019 and 2023 were calculated. Total Hazard Index is total sum of total ingestion and total dermal exposure.

For the drinking water pathway, the chronic Average Daily Intake (*ADD_{IN}*) was calculated following the standard procedure outlined in Table 2. Likewise, the dermal exposure was assessed using the calculations for average dermally absorbed dose (*ADD_{DE}*). Based on these values, HQ and HI were derived. The detailed results for each sample are presented in Table 7.

Health risk for drinking elevated F⁻ and NO₃⁻ concentration in groundwater was carried out in the Pullamapatti watershed for children and adult. The Table 7 presents the Hazard Quotient (HQ) values for fluoride (HQ_F) and nitrate (HQ_{NO₃}) exposure through oral intake and dermal exposure for children and adults across 2015, 2019, and 2023. In general, children showed higher exposure levels compared to adults, particularly for fluoride, which had ingestion (HQ_F) values ranging from 0.076 to 2.016, and dermal exposure ranging from 0.001 to 0.031. For nitrate, children's ingestion (HQ_{NO₃}) ranged from 0.553 to 3.076, with dermal exposure from 0.0085 to 0.047. Adult exposure levels were lower, with ingestion (HQ_F) values between 0.080 and 2.101, and (HQ_{NO₃}) ranging from 0.576 to 3.208. In 2023, exposure levels decreased across both fluoride and nitrate, though they still presented potential health risks, especially for children due to their heightened vulnerability.

Infants and children are particularly prone to non-carcinogenic health hazards caused by fluoride. These findings are consistent with other studies, which report that children, due to their lower body weight and higher fluoride and nitrate absorption per unit weight, face greater risks from fluoride and nitrate pollution than adults. Long-term exposure to high contaminant levels through ingestion increases the risk of health issues, including fluoride-induced neurotoxicity in developing infants and children. This emphasizes the need for effective groundwater fluoride health risk management to mitigate its impact on vulnerable populations (Mukherjee and Singh, 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). Nitrate intake can lead to various health issues in humans,

Figure 7: Land use land cover layer of Pullamapatti watershed.

Table 7: Human health risk assessment by Hazard Quotient of F⁻ and NO₃⁻ in groundwater

	Min-Max	HQ_F Ingestion	HQ_F Dermal	HQ_NO ₃ Ingestion	HQ_NO ₃ Dermal exposure
Children (2015)	Min.	0.076471	0.001176	0.552673797	0.008502674
	Max.	1.181818	0.018182	3.076203209	0.047326203
Adult (2015)	Min.	0.07971	0.0000319	0.576086957	0.000230435
	Max.	1.231884	0.000493	3.206521739	0.001282609
Children (2019)	Min.	0.194652	0.002995	0.286764706	0.004411765
	Max.	2.016043	0.031016	2.971925134	0.045721925
Adult (2019)	Min.	0.202899	0.0000812	0.298913043	0.000119565
	Max.	2.101449	0.000841	3.097826087	0.00123913
Children (2023)	Min.	0.014984	0.00107	0.026069519	0.00040107
	Max.	1.126203	0.017326	4.431818182	0.068181818
Adult (2023)	Min.	0.072464	0.000029	0.027173913	0.000289855
	Max.	1.173913	0.00047	4.619565217	0.049275362

including methemoglobinemia, neurological disorders, as well as gastric and respiratory problems. Infants, particularly those over six months old, are more vulnerable to these health risks compared to older children (Chen et al., 2016).

4.8. Total Hazard Index

The Total Hazard Index (THI) assesses health risks from ingestion and dermal exposure. The THI value ≤ 1 indicates no significant non-carcinogenic risk, while THI > 1 signifies potential non-carcinogenic health risks for the exposed population.

The THI values for adults and children over various locations in the Pullamapatti watershed are compiled (Table 8). The Total Hazard Index (THI) across various locations from 2015 to 2023 shows notable trends. Locations like Bharathipuram and Tattarhalli exhibit significant improvements, with THI dropping from 2.6 to 0.8 and 2.5 to 0.3, respectively. In contrast, Panneswara Madam witnessed an increase from 2.9 to 5.6, indicating worsening conditions. The Morappur sample showed a gradual decline from 4.1 to 2.4, while Odasalapatti improved from a peak of 3.1 in 2019 to 0.5 in 2023. These variations highlight the need for targeted groundwater management to lessen health risks.

Table 8: Total Hazard Index of F⁻ and NO₃⁻ in groundwater

	2015		2019		2023	
	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children
Location	THI		THI		THI	
Bharathipuram	2.6	2.6	1.9	1.8	0.8	0.8
Dharmapuri2	1.7	1.7	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Irumattur new	1.2	1.1	1.9	1.8	0.5	0.4
Karthankulam DW	1.9	1.8	2.2	2.1	1.6	1.5
Morappur dw	4.1	4.0	2.9	2.9	2.4	2.4
Odasalapatti	1.7	1.7	3.1	3.0	0.5	0.5
Odasalapatti x road	1.5	1.5	2.7	2.6	2.2	2.1
Karukkanchavadi	1.0	1.0	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.4
Kaveripattinam	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.0	1.0	0.9
Machinkanakottai	1.9	1.8	1.4	1.4	1.1	1.1
Papparapatti	1.7	1.6	2.4	2.3	2.1	2.0
Panneswara Madam	2.9	2.9	3.8	3.7	5.6	5.4
Tattarhalli	2.6	2.5	2.2	2.2	0.8	0.3

Human health risk assessment of F⁻ and NO₃⁻ by Total Hazard Index (THI) indicates that in 2023, 30% of the watershed area has no significant non-carcinogenic risk (THI < 1), and 70% of the area has significant non-carcinogenic health risk (THI > 1). During 2015 and 2019, more than 90% of the area had significant non-carcinogenic health risks due to fluoride and nitrate.

4.9. Conclusion

The hydrogeological and hydrochemical evaluations of the Pullamapatti watershed highlight a complex interaction between natural and human influences shaping the region's groundwater dynamics. Groundwater is predominantly stored within weathered and fractured crystalline aquifers, characterized by variable transmissivity and specific yield. Seasonal rainfall and underlying geological formations play a pivotal role in determining groundwater

recharge and water table fluctuations. Water quality analysis reveals significant geo-spatial and temporal variability, with parameters such as total dissolved solids (TDS), hardness, sodium, and fluoride often surpassing acceptable thresholds. Elevated fluoride levels, resulting from the dissolution of fluoride-bearing minerals, pose serious health concerns, including dental and skeletal fluorosis. Similarly, high nitrate concentrations, linked to agricultural runoff and domestic effluents, increase the risk of conditions like methemoglobinemia (blue baby syndrome), especially in children. The LULC studies show agriculture as the predominant activity, which, coupled with local soil characteristics, exacerbates groundwater pollution through fertilizer leaching. Although recent trends indicate a reduction in nitrate levels, concentrations in many areas still exceed safe limits, emphasizing the need for targeted remediation efforts.

Health risk assessments highlight that children are particularly vulnerable, with higher hazard indices for fluoride and nitrate exposure compared to adults. Human health risk assessment of F^- and NO_3^- by THI indicates that in 2023, 30% of the watershed area has no significant non-carcinogenic risk ($THI < 1$) and 70% of the area has significant non-carcinogenic health risk ($THI > 1$). During 2015 and 2019, more than 90% of the areas had significant non-carcinogenic health risks due to F^- and NO_3^- .

These findings underscore the urgency of implementing integrated management strategies, including regular groundwater monitoring to track contamination and aquifer changes, sustainable agricultural practices and regulated fertilizer use to curb nitrate leaching, and public health measures, such as promoting alternative drinking water sources and community education to mitigate exposure risks. Sustainable groundwater management approaches are necessary to address both quantity and quality challenges to ensure long-term water security for the Pullampatti watershed.

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Author Contributions

Divya A S - Conceptualization, Investigation and Writing Original Draft. **Joji V S** - Data Curation, Visualization, Reviewing, Editing and Supervision. **Reshma Susan Jacob** - Formal Analysis, Reviewing and Preparation of a few Maps.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors do not have any competing interest in terms of financial or personal relationship with a third party whose interests could be positively or negatively influenced by the article's content. All data used in the study was sourced by the primary and secondary data collection by the first author in connection with the research program.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are collected from the SECR, Central Ground Water Department, Chennai. The

data support the findings of this study are available from corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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